

Research on the influence of physico-chemical, hydrobiological parameters and feed consumption in the context of climate change on growth performance of *Cyprinus carpio*, Linnaeus 1758, at the Experimental Laboratory for Agrofiseries Research in Brateș

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Abstract

The development of aquaculture as an economic sector has required and continues to require the introduction of new and innovative techniques and technologies, including the optimization of technological phases for feeding target species. Carp (*Cyprinus carpio* Linnaeus, 1758) represents one of the most important culture species with high economic value. [9].

In order to optimize the technological phase of fish feeding, specifically for carp (*Cyprinus carpio* Linnaeus, 1758), under controlled aquaculture conditions, the main physicochemical parameters (water temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, nitrites, nitrates, ammonia, etc.) and hydrobiological parameters (phytoplankton and zooplankton) are assessed to ensure that they fall within appropriate limits based on the specific requirements of the species and its age.

During a 90-day experiment, the research highlighted the correlation between physicochemical and hydrobiological parameters and the food consumption of the carp species (*Cyprinus carpio* Linnaeus, 1758).

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For the purpose of conducting the research, a total of 355 specimens of carp (summer I) raised in the growth ponds of the Experimental Laboratory for Agrofiseries Research in Brateș were used as biological material. Monitoring of all parameters was carried out from April to June 2024. The methods for determining the main physicochemical parameters (water temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, nitrites, nitrates, ammonia, etc.) and hydrobiological parameters (phytoplankton and zooplankton) were specific methods described in the scientific literature. The feed used in the experiment consisted of granulated feed with a crude protein content of 27%.

It was highlighted that at temperatures exceeding 25 °C, the best feed consumption index was recorded. The lowest feed consumption index was observed at a water temperature of 18.5 °C in April, while the highest level of the consumption index was noted in August at a water temperature of 26.7 °C.

Introduction

Aquaculture as an economic sector in Romania has experienced relative stagnation over the past three decades, with only slight increases based on the application of scientific principles through the introduction of new and innovative techniques and technologies, particularly in RAS (Recirculating Aquaculture Systems) in the last decade. The current global trend in aquaculture is to increase the proportion of fish production obtained, as well as to diversify aquatic products. [1]

Considering that in recent years the level of catches from the natural environment of living aquatic resources has seen a drastic decline (with many species affected due to overfishing or pollution of natural habitats), the focus on developing aquaculture has gained increasing importance. [2].

An important aspect of modern aquaculture development is the control of the quality of technological water and feed in relation to the requirements of target fish species. This issue poses a complex challenge. [3][4][5].

The aim of the research was to highlight, in the context of climate change, the correlation between the influence of different concentrations of physicochemical and hydrobiological parameters and the feed consumption of the fish material represented by the species *Cyprinus carpio* L. 1758.

Materials and Methods

The research was conducted at the Experimental Laboratory for Agrofiseries Research in Brateș, part of the Institute for Research and Development in Aquatic Ecology, Fishing, and Aquaculture in Galați.

In the summer I growth ponds (three ponds, each with an area of 1 ha and an average depth of 1.2 m), the influence of physicochemical and hydrobiological parameters of water on feed consumption and growth performance was monitored during the vegetative period from April to June 2024, in the context of climate change. The data obtained from this experiment were compared with the data collected in 2019 from a reference pond (with an area of 1 ha and an average depth of 1.2 m), which was stocked under the same conditions and stocking formula as the experimental ponds. The analyses for the reference pond were conducted over the same time period (April to June). The year 2019 was characterized climatically as a year without significant thermal fluctuations compared to the climatic conditions of 2024. This fact, supported by the analyses, served as the basis for selecting it as the reference model.

The biological material studied consisted of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*, L. 1758) (Figure 1), at the fry stage, with an average body weight of 0.5 g per specimen, over a period of 3 months (April to June 2024), during which the carp is zooplankton-feeding.

Figure 1 – Common carp fry (*Cyprinus carpio*, L. 1758)

The growth of the biological material was conducted both in the experimental ponds and in the reference pond within a polyculture system (carp 35.5%, with the remaining species comprising bream 35% and catfish 29.5%), with a stocking density of 60,000 specimens per hectare. The research focused exclusively on the species *Cyprinus carpio*, L., analyzing a total of 355 specimens from each pond.

In order to establish the physicochemical parameters of the water, water samples were collected monthly and analyzed in the laboratory using standardized methods, titrimetric methods, the portable digital multiparameter device Hach/HQ40d (for pH, temperature, and dissolved oxygen), and the DR 2800 Hach Lange spectrophotometer (for nitrites, nitrates, ammonium, and ammonia), in accordance with Order No. 161 of February 16, 2006, for the approval of the Normative on the classification of surface water quality for the assessment of the ecological status of water bodies.

The hydrobiological analyses aimed to determine the phytoplankton and zooplankton through qualitative and quantitative microscopic analysis of samples from the three experimental ponds and the reference pond. Water collection was performed in 300 ml glass bottles from the surface layer of the water (0 m). After sampling, the specimens were preserved with Lugol's fixation solution and analyzed using the ZEISS Primo Star microscope with a Kolkwitz counting chamber, holding a capacity of 1 ml.

The feeding of the fish material was based on the use of granulated feed containing 27% crude protein and 8% lipids, appropriate for their age, with ingredients including corn, wheat, barley, sunflower, peas, and sorghum, with a granulation size of 0.5 mm. The experiment lasted for 90 days, following the same scenario as in the reference pond.

The distributed feed ratio was established as a percentage of the total biomass of the fish material and was calculated based on the water temperature and its oxygen content, representing 2% of the body weight of the fish. The feed was administered in two daily portions, given in the morning and in the evening.

Feed consumption and survival rates were monitored daily, while the assessment of the main physicochemical and hydrobiological parameters of the water was conducted monthly.

For the study and establishment of growth performance, biometric measurements were conducted on 355 fish specimens from each experimental variant. Biometric measurements were conducted at stocking, every two weeks during control fishing, and at the end of the experiment.

After weighing and measuring the individual fish specimens following the control fishing, parameters for evaluating technological performance indicators were calculated. The obtained data were utilized to determine the individual weight gain (Sr), the daily growth rate (GR), the feed conversion ratio n(FCR), and the specific growth rate (SGR) over the experimental period.

Results and Discussions

In aquaculture, profitability is dependent on the growth performance of the fish. An important indicator is represented by water quality, specifically the physicochemical and hydrobiological parameters of the water. [6,7,13].

However, exceeding the permissible limits results in undesirable side effects (stress, reduced growth rates, high mortality, etc.). [8,9,15].

Cu toate acestea, depășirea limitelor admise produce efecte secundare nedorite (stres, deprecierea creșterii, mortalitate ridicată etc)

The species *Cyprinus carpio* L. 1758 exhibited optimal growth rates at water temperatures above 20°C. In the context of climate change, the monitoring of physicochemical and hydrobiological parameters, along with daily control of feed administration, are extremely important objectives aimed at optimizing the feeding phase in order to minimize feed waste. [10,11,12,15].

The hydrochemical analysis of water samples established the evolution over time of the monthly average of the physical-chemical parameters presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Physicochemical parameters of water from experimental and control basins

Analyzed Parameters (Monthly average values)	U.M.	BR 8			BR 9			BR 10			Bazin martor		
		2024									2019		
		APR.	MAY	JUNE	APR.	MAY	JUNE	APR.	MAY	JUNE	APR.	MAY	JUNE
Temperature	°c	19,10	19,60	21,80	18,50	18,60	22,10	18,70	19,40	21,50	17,10	19,00	20,00
pH	upH	7,73	7,85	7,78	7,75	7,16	7,89	7,77	7,62	7,86	8,45	8,99	8,39
Dissolved oxygen	mg/l	12,50	11,94	8,41	11,23	9,95	10,64	13,54	13,15	7,95	11,55	9,07	7,07
Organic substance	mg KMnO ₄ /l	33,18	49,77	54,90	22,24	57,43	23,57	19,59	26,22	28,88	24,13	37,78	34,61
Calcium (Ca ²⁺)	mg/l	64,12	64,13	56,11	48,10	52,10	72,14	40,08	56,11	64,13	56,24	63,74	60,41
Magnesium (Mg ²⁺)	mg/l	34,02	21,87	19,44	26,73	24,30	41,31	58,32	51,03	21,87	39,15	26,52	25,26
Ca ²⁺ /Mg ²⁺	Raport	1,88	2,93	2,89	1,80	2,14	1,75	0,69	1,10	2,93	1,44	2,43	2,39
Total hardness	°D	16,83	14,03	12,34	12,90	12,90	19,64	19,07	19,64	14,03	16,27	14,30	13,74
Nitrites (NO ₂ ⁻)	mgN/l	0,03	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,02	0,01	0,01	0,03	0,03	0,01
Nitrates (NO ₃ ⁻)	mgN/l	0,30	0,27	0,35	0,40	0,23	0,45	0,32	0,41	0,45	1,00	0,99	0,58
Chlorides (Cl ⁻)	mg/l	12,77	12,77	12,77	9,57	9,59	9,58	15,96	12,77	9,57	145,20	121,90	126,84
Ammonium (NH ₄ ⁺)	mgN/l	0,07	0,24	0,50	0,03	0,49	0,75	0,25	0,05	0,50	0,27	0,29	0,18
Ammonia (NH ₃)	mgN/l	0,00	0,01	0,02	0,01	0,03	0,02	0,01	0,03	0,01	0,03	0,11	0,02

Figure 2 – Variation April-June 2024

The temperature variation limits of the water in the pools where the experiment was conducted ranged between 18.5 and 22.1 °C, with an average of 20.3 °C, compared to the control, where the temperature values ranged between 17.1 and 20 °C, with an average of 18.55 °C. We observe a water temperature increase gradient of almost 1.45 °C, which approaches the global value of 1.5 °C (Figure 2).

The range of water temperature variation in the ponds where the experiment was conducted was between 18.5 – 22.1 °C, with an average of 20.3 °C, compared to the reference pond, where temperature values ranged from 17.1 – 20 °C, with an average of 18.55 °C. We observe a temperature gradient increase of almost 1.45 °C, which the global value of 1.5 °C (Figure 2).

The pH generally showed an alkaline reaction, with no major fluctuations during the study period, reflecting a relatively constant composition of values over time. The reaction of the water was generally favorable for the survival of aquatic organisms, primarily fish, with values ranging from 7.16 to 7.89 upH, compared to the control, where values ranged from 8.39 to 8.45 upH.

Dissolved oxygen in water, expressed in mg/l, is one of the parameters determined for fish survival, with recorded values showing multiple fluctuations throughout the growing season. Dissolved oxygen in the analyzed samples ranged from 7.95 to 13.54 mg/l, mostly close to the maximum value. There were two cases where dissolved oxygen had a higher value, the maximum being in April of 13.54 mg/l, in BR10, without posing a problem for fish. The control sample also showed values in the range of 7.07-11.55 mg/l, falling within the values permitted by the legislation in force for second category surface waters.

The organic matter content, expressed in mg KMnO₄/l, ranged from 19.59 mg KMnO₄/l to 57.43 mg KMnO₄/l depending on the water temperature and the intensity of the decomposition processes of dead aquatic organisms. The highest organic matter content was recorded in May in BR9, and the lowest in April in BR10, compared to the control, with values ranging from 24.13 to 37.78 mg KMnO₄/l.

High levels of organic matter may be the result of the decomposition of aquatic organisms (plants and animals) due to high temperatures during the summer.

Calcium present in water, expressed in mg/l, is an element that plays a special role in the development of the organism and feeding of fish.

The minimum and maximum concentrations of the samples from the three basins showed quite large variations between 40.08 mg/l in April in BR10 and the maximum value of 72.14 mg/l in June in BR9, compared to the control, with values ranging from 56.24 to 63.74 mg/l.

Magnesium in water, expressed in mg/l, is an element that plays a special role in the development of fish organisms. It showed values between 19.44 mg/l in June in BR10 and increased in April, reaching a maximum value of 58.32 mg/l in April in BR10, compared to the control, where values ranged from 25.26 to 39.15 mg/l.

The ratio of calcium and magnesium cations, a dimensionless quantity, should ideally be 5:1 in productive water. The minimum and maximum values recorded between April and June 2024 for water samples taken from the three experimental basins showed minimum values of 2.93 mg/l in May and June in BR8 and BR10, respectively, and maximum values in August of 5.93 mg/l in BR10. The values in the control basin ranged from 1.44 to 2.43 mg/l.

Between April and June 2024, the ratio of calcium and magnesium cations is in most cases above unity, which proves the existence of a higher amount of calcium in the water compared to magnesium, these cations being the ones that will predominantly determine the hardness.

Hardness, expressed in °D (German degrees of hardness), was lower than the maximum concentration allowed by current legislation for category II surface water, i.e. 20 °D, in all cases analyzed. Nitrites, expressed in mg/l, showed a minimum value of 0.005 mg/l in June in BR8 and a maximum value of 0.03 mg/l in April in BR8 during the study period, compared to the control, with values ranging from 0.008 to 0.033 mg/l.

The nitrite concentrations determined in the three experimental basins were low compared to the maximum concentration allowed by current legislation, namely 0.2 mg/l.

Nitrates, expressed in mg/l, showed a minimum value of 0.22 mg/l in May in BR9 and a maximum value of 0.44 mg/l in June in BR9 during the study period. Both the nitrate concentrations determined in the three experimental basins and in the control had low values compared to the maximum concentration allowed by current legislation, namely 3 mg/l.

Chlorides, expressed in mg/l, showed minimum concentrations in June of 9.57 mg/l in BR10 and maximum concentrations in April of 15.96 mg/l in BR10 for the samples from the three basins, compared to the control, with values ranging from 121.9 to 145.23 mg/l.

Ammonia, expressed in mg/l, showed a minimum value of 0.05 mg/l in May in BR10 and a maximum value of 0.499 mg/l in June in BR10 during the study period.

The ammonium concentrations determined in the three experimental basins and in the control had low values compared to the maximum permissible concentration of 2 mg/l.

Ammonia, expressed in mg/l, showed a minimum value of 0.004 mg/l in April in BR8 and a maximum value of 0.033 mg/l in May in BR10 during the study period, compared to the control, with values ranging from 0.02 to 0.112 mg/l.

From the point of view of hydrobiological research, the following has been observed:

The dynamics of **phytoplankton** throughout the entire period were conditioned by the physical and chemical quality of the water and by hydrological and climatic conditions.

In the samples analyzed between April and June 2024, representatives of the following algae groups belonging to the phyla *Bacillariophyta*, *Chlorophyta*, *Euglenophyta*, and *Cyanophyta* were identified in terms of quality and quantity.

The following species of siliceous algae showed intense growth: *Amphiptera pelucida*, *Frustula rhomboides*, *Fragilaria crotonensis*, *Nitzschia sigmoidea*, *Nitzschia angustata*, *Nitzschia acicularis*, *Synedra ulna*, *Synedra acus*, *Cymbella helvetica*.

From the *Chlorophyta* taxonomic group, the identified species were represented by:

Scenedesmus quadricauda, *Pediastrum duplex*, *Pediastrum simplex*, *Selenastrum gracile*, *Oocystis parva*, *Ankistrodesmus spiralis*, *Ankistrodesmus falcatus*, *Tetraedron minimum*, *Scenedesmus opoliensis*, *Scenedesmus acuminatus*, *Treubariasetigera*, *Crucigenia quadrata*, *Crucigenia fenestrata*.

In the phytoplankton analysis, we also identified the presence of euglenophytes with the following species: *Euglena acus*, *Euglena gracilis*, *Euglena viridis*, *Phacus longicauda*.

The high temperatures recorded during the summer season when the samples were taken led to the development of cyanobacteria in the water.

Therefore, among the blue algae identified in the samples collected are: *Anabaena sphaerica* and *Microcystis viridis*.

Cyanobacteria and Euglenophyceae developed more intensely as water temperatures rose, causing a slight "bloom" in the water.

In the three experimental basins studied, diatoms and chlorophytes predominate quantitatively and qualitatively with a share of 34% and 26%, respectively, and develop throughout the year, which reveals a high trophic level of the basins. Cyanobacteria developed in 22% of the pools during the warm period, causing a slight "bloom" of the water. Euglenophytes are poorly represented throughout the study period, accounting for 18%. (Figure 3).

Figure 3 – Proportion of the main groups of algae identified between April and June 2024

The highest phytoplankton density was recorded in June: 1731.42 ex/l, due to the maximum nutrient content, high temperatures (with increased presence of chlorophytes, cyanophytes, and euglenophytes and reduced presence of diatoms) (Figure 3).

The lowest phytoplankton density was observed in April (with lower water temperatures), with species belonging to the taxonomic groups Bacillariophyta and Chlorophyta (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Evolution of phytoplankton numerical density between April and June 2024

Algal biomass recorded minimum values of 1.78 g/m^3 in April and maximum values of 10.33 g/m^3 in June.

Zooplankton is an important link in the food chains of aquatic ecosystems, constituting the most valuable food source for certain species of fish (zooplanktivores).

Along with phytoplankton, zooplankton communities make up the planktonic biocoenosis in water basins. In aquatic ecosystems, zooplankton organisms are the main consumers of plant and animal detritus suspended in the water column and on the bottom of basins, directly transforming dead organic matter into biomass for the upper trophic level.

Following the analysis of zooplankton, the existence of species grouped into three systematic groups was found: *Rotatoria*, *Copepoda*, and *Cladocera*.

Analyzing the component groups of zooplankton, it can be observed that rotifers are represented by the following species: *Keratella ticinensis*, *Keratella serulata*, *Keratella quadrata*, *Brachionus diversicornis*, *Brachionus quadridentatus*, *Brachionus urceolaris*, *Lecane cornuta*, *Brachionus rubens*, *Brachionus calyciflorus*, *Monummata longiseta*, *Trichocerca cylindria*, *Filinia longiseta*, *Platytias polyacanthus*, *Brachionus angularis*.

Copepods are represented by specimens belonging to the following species: *Macrocyclops albidus*, *Cyclops strenuus*, *Nauplii Gattung keratella*.

The following species were identified from the cladocera group: *Bosmina longirostris*, *Bosmina coregoni*, *Daphnia magna*, *Daphnia longispina*, *Moina sp.*

As regards zooplankton, the average proportion of the three experimental basins was 54% for copepods, which dominate in terms of numbers, 28% for cladocerans, and a lower proportion for rotifers, respectively 18% (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – Weighting of the main zooplankton groups identified between April and June 2024

In terms of zooplankton density, the highest density was recorded in July at 188 ex/l, and the lowest value was in April at 34 ex/l. (Figure 6)

Figure 6 – Evolution of zooplankton numerical density between April and June 2024

Zooplankton biomass evolved throughout the period analyzed from 0.26 g/m³ in April to 2.80 g/m³ in June, following the increase in temperatures and phytoplankton biomass.

The values obtained regarding the evolution of growth parameters in *Cyprinus carpio*, L. 1758, carp, from the fry stage to the average weight of the population in the three basins of 35 g/ex at the end of the experiment. The experimental data obtained on the evolution of growth parameters were used both to calculate the growth increment (Sr) in weight for each experimental period and to estimate the average daily increment (Tables 2 and 3).

Table 2 - Technological indicators at the beginning and end of the experimental period

N r. cr t.	Indicat ors	Numb er of fish speci mens in the popul ation	Avera ge weight / ex at popul ation (g)	Bioms s in popul ar cultur e (kg)	Surviv al (%)	Num ber of speci mens at harv est	Final avera ge weight (g/ex)	Total final biomass (kg)	Biomass growth rate (kg)
	Basins								
1.	BR 8	21300	0,5±0,02	10,65	80±2,14%	17040	35±2,51	596	586
2.	BR 9	21300	0,5±0,17	10,65	80±2,14%	17040	35±1,75	596	586
3.	BR 10	21300	0,5±0,05	10,65	80±2,14%	17040	35±1,90	596	586
4.	Martor	21300	0,5±0,11	10,65	85±3,10%	18105	40±2,25	724	713

Tabel nr 3. – Indicatorii de performanță a creșterii pe perioada experimentală

N r. cr t.	Indicato rs	GR (Daily growth rate) (g/zi)	SGR (%/zi)	Individ ual growth rate (g)	Total amount of feed distributed (Kg)	FCR (g fodder/g biomass increase)	Daily ration (% biomass)
	Basins						
1.	BR 8	0,39	4,64±0,07	34,46	39,70	0,7±0,16	2,0
2.	BR 9	0,39	4,40±0,08	34,46	39,70	0,7±0,12	2,0
3.	BR 10	0,39	4,83±0,10	34,46	39,70	0,7±0,08	2,0
4.	Referenc e	0,44	4,65±0,04	39,47	39,70	0,6±0,28	2,0

With regard to food consumption, a clear correlation was observed between water temperature, the amount of food consumed, and weight gain. There were no significant differences between the three experimental tanks. The individual weight gain of the fish and their final average body mass after 90 days of experimentation was 596 kg in BR8, BR9, and BR10 (Table 2), but differences were found compared to the control tank, where the total biomass obtained was 724 kg, a tank where temperature fluctuations were not as sudden as during the experiment period.

Regarding the specific growth rate (SGR) and feed conversion ratio (FCR), the best values were obtained in the control variant. The results showed that the SGR values in BR8 (4.64±0.07%/day) were similar to those in BR9 (4.40±0.08%/day) and BR10 (4.83±0.10%/day) compared to the control variant 4.65±0.04%/day. As for FCR, it ranged from 0.07±0.16 in BR 8, BR 9, and BR 10 to 0.06±0.28 in the control variant (Table no. 3).

Survival is an important indicator of fish health [6]. In our experiments, survival was directly influenced by the physical, chemical, and hydrobiological parameters of the water. The results showed that the survival rate of fish in tanks BR8, BR9, and BR10 was $80 \pm 2.14\%$, compared to the control variant, where the survival rate was 5% higher, respectively $85 \pm 3.1\%$.

Conclusions

The analysis of the physical and chemical parameters carried out over the three months in the experimental basins did not reveal any natural nowcasting phenomena, with the data obtained showing that these were within the normal limits for surface waters, but in higher concentrations (given the higher average temperatures compared to the control) and did not endanger the survival of the fish. However, a decrease in growth was observed compared to the control.

From a quantitative point of view, it can be observed throughout the study period that the proportion of plankton biomass is generally proportional to numerical density. There are also discrepancies in certain periods between the proportions of phytoplankton biomass and its density. Zooplankton is an important link in the trophic networks of aquatic ecosystems and has followed an evolution correlated with that of phytoplankton.

We observe that in 2019, cladocera are better represented in terms of numbers and proportion than in 2024, their biomass being extremely important in the growth rate (SGR) of carp, which was higher in 2019.

The research showed that at the end of the experimental period, the carp reached an average weight of 35 g/ex, compared to 40 g/ex in the control basin. It should be noted that in the control pond, due to the hydrochemical conditions and temperatures without significant fluctuations, the zooplankton base (especially cladocerans, which are particularly important in carp nutrition) increased considerably compared to the experimental ponds. These studies are preliminary research, which will be continued under the same technological conditions over a long period of time in order to study the evolution over time, under conditions of climate change.

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